

OCEAN:ICE News – February 2025

OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN:ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to February's edition of OCEAN:ICE News. We're excited to bring you the latest updates from the OCEAN:ICE community.

In this issue, you'll meet our featured researcher of the month and catch up on key activities, including celebrating an OCEAN:ICE publication and a new Explain it in Two Ways series on Tipping Elements and Tipping Points. We have upcoming Climate Coffees that you can register for in February, March, April, May and June. Don't forget to mark your calendars for the upcoming events where OCEAN:ICE will be represented.

We hope you enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to sharing more in March!

Researcher in the Spotlight: Max Brils

Check out our latest 'Researcher in the Spotlight' feature on Max Brils, post-doctoral researcher working at [Northumbria University](#) in the UK.

Read the feature on Max [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN:ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN:ICE Activities

OCEAN:ICE Explain it in Two Ways series: Tipping Elements and Tipping Points

We are thrilled to continue our collaboration with PolarRES on the video series 'Explain it in Two Ways'!

This series aims to break down complex scientific processes for both the general public and scientific audiences, offering valuable insights from our researchers.

This instalment includes [Torsten Albrecht](#) and [Tony Payne](#) from OCEAN:ICE.

You can read the article and view the Explain it in Two Ways series [here](#).

OCEAN:ICE
EXPLAIN IT
IN TWO WAYS

OCEAN ICE is co-funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation. Disclaimer: The content of this video reflects only the views of the individuals featured. The European Commission and UK Research and Innovation are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

OCEAN:ICE Paper

On December 19th last year an OCEAN:ICE publication was released in the Journal Nature: "Record Low Antarctic Sea-Ice in 2023 Increased Ocean Heat Loss and Storms", by Simon A. Josey, Andrew J. S. Meijers, Adam T. Blaker, Jeremy P. Grist, Jenny Mecking & Holly C. Ayres. This research was initially conceived at the OCEAN:ICE/SO-CHIC workshop in 2023 and led by Simon Josey at the UK National Oceanography Centre.

Read the article covering a summary of the paper here: [OCEAN:ICE Paper – Record Low Antarctic Sea-Ice in 2023 Increased Ocean Heat Loss and Storms - OCEAN:ICE](#)

 OCEAN:ICE

OCEAN:ICE Paper Published:

Record Low Antarctic Sea-Ice in 2023 Increased Ocean Heat Loss and Storms

 Funded by the European Union

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Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't you worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Upcoming Event

Climate Coffee

We have five upcoming Climate Coffee events, make sure you register for all of them through the link on [OCEAN:ICE](https://ocean.ice.eu).

Climate Coffee with Beatrice Maddalena Scotto on Multi-Model Framework for Tracking Pollutant Dispersion in the Mediterranean Sea

20 February 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CET)

20 February 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET
Online

Beatrice Maddalena Scotto (ETT)

**Multi-Model Framework for Tracking
Pollutant Dispersion in the
Mediterranean Sea**

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

Climate Coffee with Sofia Darmaraki on Marine Heatwaves in the Mediterranean Sea: A Literature Review

20 March 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CET)

20 March 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET
Online

Sofia Darmaraki (FORTH)

**Marine Heatwaves in the Mediterranean
Sea: A Literature Review**

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

Climate Coffee with David Chandler on Warming of circumpolar deep water
16 April 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CET)

16 April 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online

Dave Chandler (NORCE)

Warming of circumpolar deep water: a million-year perspective on recent changes around Antarctica

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

Climate Coffee with Inga Sauer on Extreme weather events: tipping points & societal implications
22 May 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

22 May 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online

Inga Sauer (PIK)

Extreme weather events: tipping points and societal implications

The poverty implications of increasing frequencies of extreme weather events - identifying tipping points across households from different income groups

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

Climate Coffee with Amen Al-Yaari on Recent AMOC variations and the implications for the future (tbc)
19 June 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

19 June 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online
Amen Al-Yaari (University Bordeaux)
Recent AMOC variations and the implications for the future (tbc)

Danish Meteorological Institute

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the European Union

OCEAN:ICE at ASSW (Arctic Science Summit Week) 2025

OCEAN:ICE will be represented at ASSW (Arctic Science Summit Week) through a presentation about data flow and ocean data management in Europe. It will look at how projects like OCEAN:ICE, POLARIN and others are synergic and crucial to make data accessible, especially in remote areas.

Happening Soon

OCEAN:ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 20-28 March 2025, [Arctic Science Summit Week \(ASSW\) 2025](#), Boulder, Colorado (USA)
- 20th of February 2025, OCEAN:ICE represented at the kick off meeting for ICELINK Copenhagen, (Denmark)

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN:ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

Are you following us on Social Media?

Stay up to date with OCEAN:ICE on our following channels:

www.ocean-ice.eu

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/euoceanice/>

https://twitter.com/OCEANICE_EU

<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

<https://www.facebook.com/OCEANICEEU/>

Who is OCEAN:ICE?

OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN:ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

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